

EVALUATION OF VERB DERIVATION SUFFIXES IN CHAGATAY, UZBEK AND NEW UYGUR TURKISH IN TERMS OF CONSONANT HARMONY

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Sounds, which are the basic building blocks of languages, are of great importance for a language, as they not only play a role in the formation of many words, but also in the formation of numerous suffixes in the language. The way sounds come together to fulfill their duties is not a coincidence, but based on a certain harmony. Karaağaç G., [2018: 817] “All sounds derive their identities from their place of origin and form of origin. Where and how sounds are produced in the vocal organs are the two main forms of sound changes. The harmony or disharmony between sounds, that is, similarity or dissimilarity, occurs within these two scales; but not both at the same time. Similarity or dissimilarity occurs either according to where the sounds originate or according to their forms. He talks about this harmony by saying, “Sound harmony is the harmony of sounds according to where they come from or how they come from.” Therefore, there are three harmony that the sounds must obey when forming word roots and stems. These harmony are vowel harmony, vowel-consonant/consonant-vowel harmony and consonant harmony.

Korkmaz Z., [2009; 575] defined consonant-consonant harmony, which is the main subject of the study, as the harmony based on the compatibility of two consonants in terms of voicelessness and unvoicedness during the expansion of words with suffixes or in adjacent syllables in Turkish; Ergin M., [2013: 75-76] explained consonant harmony as the compatibility of two consonants in terms of vibration in words. While there is no contradiction in the harmony of adjacent

sounds in consonant harmony in terms of tone, the fact that the use of voiced consonants (/l/, /m/, /n/, /r/, /y/), which do not have a voiceless equivalent, is considered harmonious with both voiced and voiceless consonants creates a contradiction. Considering its use compatible creates a contradiction. In our opinion, these structures that are considered to be in harmony (toneless + toned sounds that do not have a toneless equivalent) should actually be considered as discordant structures.

Within the scope of the study, attention was paid to the existence of the use of the suffixes evaluated in all three dialects (Chagatai, Uzbek and New Uyghur Turkish). The harmony of tone and voicelessness between the first sounds of the suffixes added to the root and stem of the word and the last sound of the word was examined. If it was determined that the tone form of the suffix only came on voiced

consonants, the harmony of tone; if it was determined that the voiceless form only came on voiceless consonants, the harmony of voicelessness; of the suffixes used in two forms as voiced and voiceless, the harmony of tone forms with voiced and voiceless forms with voiceless was evaluated as conforming to consonant harmony, and the opposite uses were evaluated as contradictory to consonant harmony.

Detected Attachments

1.1. +GAR-

Çağ.+kar- başkar-: to start, kütkar-: to save, sıpkar-: to drink quickly, taşkar-: to go out (ÇT, 133); Özb. +gar-/+kar- cemgar-: to collect piece by piece, başkar-: to carry out (ÖTG, 74); Y. Uyg. +kar-/+ker- başkar-: to manage, eskert-: to remind (YUTG, 42).

1.2. +GXr-

Çağ.+ğır-/+kir- inçkir-: to cry in a low voice, kıçğır-: to call (ÇT, 133; LM, 220); Özb. +kır-/+kir- eykır-: to shout, keçkir-: to be late, kıyıkır-: to shout (ÖTG, 75); Y. Uyg. +kür-çüçkür-: to sneeze, öñkür-: to cry (YUTG, 44).

1.3. +KXRa-

Çağ. +küre- ürküre-: to doze (ÇT, 133); Özb. +dire-/+kıra-/+kire- gürkire-: to catch up, şerkıra-: make water sound, şavdire-: to flow with a loud noise, valdire-: to speak out, diydire-: to tremble, gildire-: to appear faint (ÖTG, 74-75; ÖTGMS, 38); Y. Uyg. +gira-/+kira-/+küre-/+cira-/+cura-/+çire- gañgira-: to be surprised, gürküre-: to rumble, varkıra-: to shout loudly, culcura-: to wear out, kaçcira-: to dry out, tepçire-: drip (YUTG, 42-44).

1.4. +DA-

Çağ. +da-/+de-/te-/ta-alda-: to deceive, dökülde-: get excited, iste-: to want, to seek, yasta-: lean on (ÇT, 132; ÇEK, 112); Özb.+de- ünde-: to invite (ÖTG, 74; ÖTGMS, 38); Y. Uyg. +da-/+de- alda-: to deceive, ceynekde-: to lean one's arm, kövükde-: to foam (YUTG, 42).

1.5. +lA-

Çağ.+la-/+le- ağırla-: to host, bağışla-: to forgive, birle-: to unite, söyle-: to say, başla-: to begin, közle-: to observe (ÇT, 133); Özb. +le- işle-: to process, söyle-: to say, teşle-: to throw, oyle-: to think (ÖTG, 75; ÖTGMS, 38); Y. Uyg. +la-/+le- kırkurla-: gurgle, alkışla-: to applaud, cemle-: to collect, ayhayla-: to grumble (YUTG, 44).

1.6. +lAn-

Çağ.+lan-/+len- ağlan-: to be sad, atlan-: to ride a horse, yüzlen-: to turn, sallan-: to swing (ÇT, 133); Özb. +lan- cânlen-: to revive, ümidlen-: to hope (ÖTG, 75); Y. Uyg. +lan-/+len- cüretlen-: to dare, kansızlan-: to remain bloodless, üylen-: to get married (YUTG, 45).

1.7. +lAş-

Çağ.+laş- muñlaş-: telling each other about one's troubles (ÇT, 113); Özb. +leş- köpleş-: to be mostly, ağırleş-: to become heavy (ÖTG, 75); Y. Uyg. +leş- aqtiwleş-: to become active, geleş-: to talk, yüzleşmek-: to come face to face (YUTG, 45).

1.8. +lAt-

Çağ. +lat-/+let- sözlet-: to make someone say, aňlat-: to tell (ÇT, 134); Özb. +let- aydinlet-: to illuminate, qalinlet-: to thicken (ÖTG, 75); Y. Uyg. +lat-/+let- canlat-: to animate, köpüklet-: to foam, tumanlat-: to smoke (YUTG, 45).

1.9. +rA-

Çağ.+ra- möñre -: bleating, siñre-: crying secretly in sorrow (ÇT, 134); Özb. +ra-/+re- hengre-: to bray, qakra-: to dry, ingre-: to moan, yeltire-: to shine (ÖTG, 76; ÖTGMS, 38); Y. Uyg. +ra- aňra-: looking confused, haňra-: braying (YUTG, 45).

2.10. +sA-

Çağ.+sa- qapsa-: to cover, bohsa-: to cry from longing in love (ÇT, 134); Özb. +se- buruqse-: to smoke, suvse-: to thirst (ÖTG, 76); Y. Uyg. +sa-/+se- deñse-: to weigh, vaysa-: to chatter (YUTG, 45).

2.11. +sI-

Çağ.+si- köksi-: to rise to the sky; Özb. +si- gerengsi-: being deaf, mensi-: be inferior, siyraqsı-: become rare, ivirsi-: walking silently (ÖTG, 76; ÖTGMS, 38); Y. Uyg. +si-/+sü - ademsi-: selling greatness, biksi-: getting dirty, öksü-: to feel sad (YUTG, 46).

2.12. -GAR-

Çağ.-gar-/qar- bütker-: to finish, yatqar-: lay down, toygar-: satiate (ÇT, 135); Özb. -ker-/qaz-/kez- bitkez-: to finish, tolgaz-: to fill, qazqaz-: to wait ötker-: to spend, yetker-: to cultivate (ÖTG, 77-79; ÖTGMS, 39); Y. Uyg. -qar-/qaz- toşqar-: to overflow, toşqaz-: to overflow, tuqqaz-: to give birth (YUTG, 53-54).

2.13. -GXr/-GXz-

Çağ.-ğuz-/güz-/quz- azğur-: to arouse, yetkür-: to cultivate, yatğur-: to announce, yatqar-: to lay down (ÇT, 135); Özb. -ğır-/kir-/gız-/giz-/qız-/kiz azğır-: to arouse, keçkir-: to be late, ketkiz-: to relieve, tolgız-: to fill, yetkiz-: to be able, kirgiz-: insert (ÖTG, 78; ÖTGMS, 39); Y. Uyg. -gür-/quz-/güz- kirgür-: insert, yatquz-: to lay down, küydürgüz-: to dress (YUTG, 53-54).

2.14. -DAR-

Çağ.-tar-ahtar-: to research (ÇT, 134); Özb. -ter- tönter-: to turn (ÖTG, 81); Y. Uyg. -dar-/dur-/tar- toldur-: to fill, aqdar-/ahtar-/ahtar-: to turn, toştar-: to overflow (YUTG, 53).

2.15. -DXr -

Çağ. -dur-/dür-/tur-/tür- aqtur-: to pour out, aldır-: to cause to be taken, bildür-: to inform, oquttur-: to make people read, keltür-:to bring(ÇT, 135); Özb. -dir-/tir- açdir-: to open, oqırdır-:to make people read, tanışdır-: to introduce someone to

someone else, yeçintir-: to solve (ÖTG, 77; ÖTGMS, 39); Y. Uyg. -dür-/-tur-/-tür- mindür-: to mount, aşurttur: to increase, kirgüzdür-: to make someone enter, öltür-: to kill (YUTG, 53).

2.16. -lA-/-tA-

Çağ.-le- derle-: compile (AD, 458); Özb. -le-/-te- bükle-: to bend, kiste-: to force (ÖTG, 79-80); Y. Uyg. -le- kesle-: to cut (YUTG, 55).

3. Conclusion

Within the scope of the study, the common use of 16 suffixes used as noun-to-verb suffixes and verb-to-verb suffixes were determined in Chagatai, Uzbek and New Uyghur Turkish. When the consonant harmony of these identified suffixes was evaluated;

+GAr- suffix was used without tone in Chagatai and New Uyghur Turkish. The use of the suffix only with toneless consonants shows that it complies with toneless harmony. In Uzbek Turkish, the suffix was used in toned and toneless forms, and the use of toned forms with tones and toneless forms with toneless forms shows that the suffix was used by adapting to consonant harmony.

+GXr-; +KXR-; The +lA- suffix was used without adapting to consonant harmony in the dialects whose examples were identified.

The +DA- suffix shows that the suffix, which is used in both voiced and voiceless forms in Chagatai Turkish, was used in accordance with the consonant harmony of the suffix. The suffix, which is used with its tonal forms in Uzbek and New Uyghur Turkish, was used only with voiced consonants in Uzbek Turkish, complying with the tone harmony, whereas in New Uyghur Turkish, it was not used in accordance with the suffix consonant harmony, as it was also detected to be used with unvoiced consonants.

+lAn-; The +rA- suffix, in its tonal form in Chagatai and New Uyghur Turkish, was used only with voiced consonants, indicating that it was used in accordance with intonation harmony. The use of the suffix with its toned form in Uzbek Turkish, both with and without tones, shows that the suffix is not used in accordance with consonant harmony.

+lAş- suffix, in its tonal form in Chagatai Turkish, is used only with voiced consonants, indicating that it is used in accordance with intonation harmony. The use of the suffix in its tonal form in Uzbek and New Uyghur Turkish with both tones and tonless shows that the suffix is not used in accordance with consonant harmony.

The +lAt- suffix, in its tonal form in Chagatai and Uzbek Turkish, is used only with voiced consonants, indicating that it is used in accordance with intonation harmony. The use of the suffix with its tonal form in New Uyghur Turkish, both with and without tones, shows that the suffix is not used in accordance with consonant harmony.

+sA-; +sI- suffix, in its toneless form in Chagatai Turkish, shows that the suffix is used only with toneless consonants in accordance with toneless harmony. The use of the suffix, which is used in its toneless form in Uzbek and New Uyghur Turkish, with both tones and untone, shows that the suffix is not used in accordance with consonant harmony.

-GAr-/-KAr- suffix, which was used with toned and toneless forms in Chagatai and Uzbek Turkish, shows that the suffix was used by adapting the consonant harmony to the consonant harmony of the suffix in Chagatai Turkish. In Uzbek Turkish, it is seen that the suffix was used without adapting to consonant harmony. The fact that the suffix, which is used in its toneless form in New Uyghur Turkish, is used only with toneless consonants shows that it is used in accordance with toneless harmony.

-GXr-/-GXz- suffix; While it is seen that the suffix, which is used in its toned and untone forms in Chagatai, Uzbek and New Uyghur Turkish, was used in accordance with the consonant harmony in Uzbek and New Uyghur Turkish, it was used without adapting to the consonant harmony in Chagatai Turkish.

-DAr- suffix is used in its toneless form in Chagatai and Uzbek Turkish, in Chagatai Turkish, its use only with toneless ones complies with toneless harmony, whereas in Uzbek Turkish it is not used in accordance with consonant harmony. The use of the suffix with toned and toneless forms in New Uyghur Turkish shows that the suffix is used in accordance with the consonant harmony.

-DXr- suffix was used without adapting to consonant harmony in the dialects whose examples were identified.

-lA- suffix, in its tonal form in Chagatai Turkish, is used only with toned consonants, indicating that it is used in accordance with toneless harmony. The use of the suffix in its toned form in Uzbek and New Uyghur Turkish with both tones and toneless shows that the suffix is not used in accordance with consonant harmony.

The suffixes found to be used in Chagatai, Uzbek and New Uyghur Turkish generally operated without adapting to the consonant harmony in the dialects that are the subject of the study. No examples have been found in which any of the suffixes followed are compatible in all dialects.

Source

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